

GONADOTROPIN-RELEASING HORMONE ANALOGUES: COMPARING LONG AND SHORT PROTOCOL IN IVF OUTCOMES AT PRINCE RASHED MILITARY HOSPITAL

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Abstract: Objective: To examine whether the outcomes of IVF cycles would vary according to the selected stimulation protocol. Method: The subjects of this retrospective descriptive inquiry are infertile patients who completed IVF treatment cycles at the Prince Rashed Military Hospital from May 2022 to February 2023. Comparisons were drawn between different stimulation protocols using GnRH analogues. The variables examined included the rate of pregnancy, rate of cancellation, total dosage of gonadotropin needed to affect stimulation, levels of serum estradiol on hCG administration day, total of follicles punctured, complexes that have been retrieved, total of oocytes that have matured, as well as attained embryos. Results: The cycle outcomes based on the stimulation protocol used for the studied variables showed no statistically significant differences. Conclusion: There are no differences in the IVF cycle outcomes with the use of GnRH analogues. Further research with larger sample sizes is necessary to identify the optimal treatment for each patient to achieve the best results.

Keywords: GnRH analogues, Pregnancy rate.

Introduction:

Gonadotropin-Releasing Hormone (GnRH) analogs bind to GnRH receptors, initially stimulating increased release of gonadotropins [1]. These medications offer several advantages, including preventing premature LH surges, reducing cycle cancellations due to spontaneous ovulation, facilitating precise scheduling of follicular punctures, and promoting synchronized follicular development [2]. However, higher rates of ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome have been linked to their usage which necessitates higher doses of gonadotropins [3].

Meanwhile, the GnRH antagonists block the GnRH receptors [4], leading to an immediate suppression of gonadotropin release and enabling ovarian stimulation to coincide with follicular recruitment [5]. There is ongoing debate about whether the choice of stimulation protocol affects outcomes in in vitro fertilization (IVF) cycles [6]. This research intends to explore such potential differences.

Materials and Methods:

Patients:

A total of 335 IVF cycles performed in the Reproduction Service of the Prince Rashed Military Hospital are analyzed between the months of between May 2022 and February 2023. 35 infertile patients were excluded from the main sample (This exclusion was conducted randomly to maintain the integrity of the study's design). The inclusion criteria in terms of age were patients under 40 years of age; BMI between 18 and 35 Kg/m²; number of previous IVF cycles less than 2.

Stimulation Protocol:

Two groups of patients were formed according to the stimulation protocol given to them. A total of 200 patients makes up the first group which followed a long protocol with GnRH analogs, entailing desensitization starting from day 22 of the previous cycle and stimulation with FSH beginning on the third day. Meanwhile, a total of 100 patients makes up the second group which followed a short protocol with GnRH antagonists, where the FSH-based stimulation started on the second or third day. Once the leading follicle turned 14 mm in size, the administration of the GnRH antagonists commenced.

Hormonal Determinations:

The FSH and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) values were analyzed before starting the stimulation cycle and serum estradiol on the day of puncture.

Statistical Analysis:

The SPSS software was used to conduct the statistical analysis, with the data denoted in the form of mean $\pm$ standard deviation ($\pm$ SD). The Chi-square test, Mann-Whitney U test, and Wilcoxon W test were carried out to identify the statistically significant differences which are demonstrated by a P value of 0.05 and less.

Results:

A total of 300 IVF treatment cycles commenced from May 2022 to February 2023 at the Reproduction Service of Prince Rashed Military Hospital. The patients had a median age of 37.53, with their ages ranging between 23 and 40 years old. A total of 200 simulation cycles used the GnRH agonists-based long stimulation protocol, while the remaining 100 used a short protocol with GnRH antagonists. The mean age of the patients in the two groups showed a statistically significant difference of one year namely (35.34) years in the group that used agonists, versus (37.25) years in the group that used antagonists. No differences were observed in relation to the ovarian reserve documented as number of antral follicles, basal FSH and AMH. This fact supports the homogeneity of the groups and gives consistency to the results. A total of 94 pregnancies were achieved, which represents a pregnancy rate of 31.3%.

Pregnancy Rate According to Stimulation Protocol:

Based on the stimulation protocol used, the pregnancy rates showed no statistically significant differences ($P=0.834$). The group assigned with long protocol using agonists had a pregnancy rate of 33.4%, whilst the group treated with the short protocol using antagonists had a pregnancy rate of 32.3%.

Cycle Cancellation Rate According to Stimulation Protocol:

The cancellations rate as adjusted by stimulation protocol showed no statistically significant differences ($P=0.526$). In the group using the long protocol with agonists, 4.1% of the cycles were canceled while in the short protocol group with antagonists, 6.9% of the cycles were canceled. The rate of cancellation slightly increased in the group treated with short protocol with antagonists, but because the total number of cancellations was very low (35 cancellations), these differences do not reach statistical significance.

Other Parameters:

The total dose of FSH required for stimulation was higher in the group using GnRH analogues, despite being non-statistically significant ($p=0.724$). There were no significant differences in the levels of serum

estradiol on the follicular puncture day ($p=0.342$), although they were slightly higher in cases using the long protocol. Additionally, the total follicles punctured ($p=0.319$), number of retrieved complexes ($p=0.895$), number of mature oocytes ($p=0.720$), and number of embryos obtained ($p=0.811$) also showed no significant differences (Table 1).

Ovarian Reserve:

A higher pregnancy rate was noted based on ovarian reserve factors such as age, basal FSH, AMH, and number of antral follicles, independent of the stimulation protocol employed.

Discussion:

There are three types of protocols involving GnRH agonists: the long protocol (agonist administered from the previous cycle's luteal phase), the short protocol (agonist administered between the cycle's first and third day, utilizing the flare-up effect), and the ultra-short protocol (agonist administered only during the first three days of the cycle).

There are also two distinct protocols involving GnRH antagonists [7,8,9]. The multiple-dose protocol starts antagonist administration on the sixth day of ovarian stimulation or when a follicle reaches a minimum diameter of 14 mm, continuing to hCG administration day with a 0.25 mg/day dosage. Contrarily, in the single-dose protocol, the GnRH antagonist is administered at a single dose once the largest follicle reaches a diameter of 14 mm, at a minimum dose of 3 mg.

In this study we have only compared the results of IVF cycles in cases where long protocols with GnRH analogues and short multiple-dose protocols with antagonists were used.

Pregnancy rates depending on the stimulation protocol used [10]. In this study we have not observed statistically significant differences. This result agrees with those obtained in most publications [11,12,13]. However, there are other studies in which lower pregnancy rates have been observed, in cases in which a stimulation protocol with GnRH antagonists had been used [14,15].

Many studies document differences in cycle characteristics, such as longer treatment duration, increased doses of gonadotropins, and higher levels of estradiol on the hCG administration day for groups using the GnRH agonist protocol [16,17]. In this current study, although these differences were non-statistically significant, the trend indicates higher gonadotropin doses and elevated estradiol levels in the GnRH agonist group. With a larger sample size, these differences might become statistically significant.

In the study by Salameh, Faour, & Awwad, published in 2022 [18], better follicular growth and oocyte maturation were documented in cases in which a protocol with GnRH agonists had been used. We have not observed statistically significant differences in this regard. However, although without reaching statistical significance, there was a greater number of mature oocytes used in the GnRH antagonist treatment group albeit with a smaller number of embryos.

Most studies indicate that patients treated with GnRH antagonists showed a lower prevalence of ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome in the moderate to severe scale [19,20]. This may be attributed to the ovulation stimulation ability using a GnRH agonist in cases of high-risk ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome. In our current study, no differences were observed in cycle cancellations caused by ovarian hyperstimulation syndrome risks based on the type of protocol used.

Table 1 Parameters under evaluation based on the stimulation protocol

	Long agonist	Short agonist	P value
Total FSH dose (IU)	2357.63 ± 924.72	2128.49 ± 802.49	0.724
Estradiol-puncture (pg/ml)	1829.47 ± 1398.87	1618.82 ± 1282.82	0.342
Number of follicles punctured	11.43 ± 5.78	12.54 ± 7.21	0.319
Number of complexes obtained	8.17 ± 5.89	9.75 ± 5.81	0.895
Number of mature oocytes	6.63 ± 3.48	8.12 ± 5.01	0.720
Number of embryos	5.96 ± 4.69	4.89 ± 4.51	0.811

Conclusion:

The findings of this study indicate no significant differences in the IVF outcomes between the groups using GnRH analogues and antagonists in the long or short protocol. The existing literature presents mixed findings on pregnancy rates, but most studies indicate no notable differences. Further research with larger sample sizes is necessary to identify which patients might benefit more from each treatment for optimal results.

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